

A QUALITY OF WORK LIFE TOWARDS WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

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ABSTRACT

This investigation takes into account the impact of the employee's work-life quality. The author surveyed 150 employees from a total of 600 employees. The overall purpose is to research employee quality of life in various facets such as job role, acknowledgement via employee participation, and professional growth, which will help organizations solve the problem of employee quality of life. This report was created after extensive research and is based on information provided by company personnel as well as a questionnaire filled out by employees. The data was tabulated and analysed using various statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Chi-square test, and weighted average. After evaluating the information, the researcher developed conclusions and recommendations for the company.

Key words: work life, Chi-square test, job role, employee participation

INTRODUCTION

The consideration of working quality Life is the larger context for various workplace factors including work satisfaction and mental anguish, which may hold promise for more economical workplace interventions. Employers under pressure to meet governmental requirements, for example, may find it impossible to target stress reduction effectively. They categorised working life quality as meeting these key needs through resources, events, and consequences resulting from workplace engagement. Needs as described by psychologist Abraham Maslow were "deemed relevant in underpinning this model, covering health and safety, economic and family, social, esteem, actualisation, knowledge, and aesthetics, though the relevance of non-work aspects is minimised because attention is focused on quality of work life rather than the broader concept of quality of life (Maslow, 12)".

The favorableness or unfavorability of a job environment for people is referred to as QWL. The primary goal is to create work environments that are both good for people and good for the

organization's financial health. "When firms focused on the problem of work-life balance, they always achieved significant productivity gains."

There are many elements in a QWL program includes:

- Transparent communication
- A fair reward system
- Enforcement of Job security
- Partaking in work plan - career augmentation & structural design
- Workers' skill advancement
- Occupational stress reduction
- Healthy employer-employee relations
- A thought-provoking job
- More prospect for development

OBJECTIVE:

The primary objective of the investigation is

- To improve the effectiveness of work-life quality.
- To identify the employment factors that influence work-life quality.
- To find the interpersonal relation.
- To find the motivation factor.
- To know the opinion of employee's towards the working hours and environment.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This investigation helps to find out the satisfaction level of employees towards their occupation, working environment, fringe benefits, and salary and working hours. The scope of the study has an impact on shaping the employees personality, determining the performance. It helps to find out the nature of support from the superiors/managers to the employees in their job. The research contributes to an improvement in the quality of life at work..

NEED OF THE STUDY

The study's need is for the continuous improvement from both individual and organizational objectives. It contributes to a pleasant work atmosphere. Career Development Opportunities and increasing Workers participative in management, improves the effectiveness of the Company's present Quality of Work Life Strategy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Jyothilakshmi., Dr.Ebby JosephIdicula.(2017) in paper titled “Literature review on QWL”, it is clear that the significance of the term becomes higher from period to period. It is assured that the efficiency and productivity of any organization can be improved by implementing higher QWL. As compared to the organizations without QWL, the firms having QWL excel in their performance. The scope of QWL in research is expanding as the concept's relevance and implementation in the business and corporate world develop. Many dimensions of work life quality remain unexplored, including organisational profitability and expansion as well as personal characteristics.
2. A.Vasumathi (2018), in her study “Work life Balance of Women employees”, Women in many developed countries face a variety of issues, including sexual and psychical harassment at work, safety concerns when travelling by various transportation methods after work hours, flexi work hours, child care facilities, non-cooperation from family members, and gender bias in promotional policies and decision making. Aside from these issues, many working women successfully balance dual roles (work and family) and solve day-to-day problems in both work and family life. All working women receive help from family organisations, and government policies for their problems and take appropriate actions to resolve their various issues in order to balance their work and life, which leads to a peaceful life in work and family and paves the way for the country's hyper growth and development.
3. Tahani H. Alqahtani (2020) in paper titled “Work Life Balance of Women employees a lreview of literature”, It's indeed evident from the preceding literature that many antecedents of WLB are found in many studies conducted in this area. Furthermore, it has been made clear that a better WLB has several beneficial outcomes, whereas an individual's imbalance between work and family has a detrimental impact, which is fully accountable for some severe problems for both the individual and the organisation.
4. Neha Poddar, Dr. Prakash Divakaran (2020) studied “Work life Balance of Working women” According to the study, there are a wide range of variables that influence women's roles when faced with various challenges in balancing career and family responsibilities. These factors are crucial in determining the key challenges of female managers and their dual role of balancing career and family responsibilities. The researcher's investigation provides a strong perspective on the career and family responsibilities of female managers in order to maintain WLB and address key issues confronting working women.

METHODOLOGY

This methodology has been used to improve the quality of women's work lives in order to empower women.

Research

It is a systematic and scientific search for relevant data on a particular subject. It is either an artistic or clinical exploration.

Research Design

The descriptive research method was used in this study. The research is carried out using a structured questionnaire that includes both close - ended and open questions. The findings, thus obtained were tabulated analyzed and interpreted, suggestions and recommendations were given in the analysis.

Descriptive research

Statistical research, as it is also known, provides information and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being investigated. Descriptive research provides answers to the following questions: who, what, where, when, and how... In a nutshell, descriptive research is concerned with anything that can be measured and investigated. However, there are always limitations.

Sampling

The study was conducted with a sample of hundred and fifty respondents. The investigation was a descriptive one. The convenience sampling method was used for the study.

Sources of data

Primary as well as secondary data is used to collect information necessary to satisfy the objective of the study.

Primary Data:

The structured questionnaire was the main sources of primary data.

Secondary data:

Various journals, Periodicals, Books, Websites etc were used for reference to obtain information for the project.

Mode of study

The survey method was used for this study. Structured questionnaire was used to collect information from employees by filling questionnaire through direct conversation with respondents. There were opportunities to record all relevant information and opinions that surfaced during the conversation with respondents. Thus valuable insights in to different views of employees could be gained.

Analytical tools used

The statistical analyses were performed utilising basic statistical models such as the percentage method and Chi-square.

Chi-square test

“A chi-square test (also chi squared test or χ^2 test) is any statistical hypothesis test in which the sampling distribution of the test statistic is a [[chi- the chi-square distribution is approximately valid ()”.

Formula:

Degree of freedom,

$$Df = (r-1)*(c-1)$$

Where r= no of rows,
 and c=no of columns.

Sampling

“Sampling is the part of statistical practise concerned with selecting a subset of individuals from a population in order to gain some knowledge about the entire population, particularly for the purpose of making predictions based on statistical inference ()”.

Questionnaire

“A questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions and other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents ()”.

Sample Size

The representative sample is 150 people out of a total of 350.

**STATISTICAL ANALYSIS
 CHI SQUARE TEST (Ψ^2)**

I. Relation between age and the safety measures provided by the company

Ho: There is no correlation between age and the company's safety measures.

H1: There is corelation between age and the safety measures provided by the company.

OBSERVED VALUES (O)

	BELOW 25	BETWEEN 25-35 YEARS	BETWEEN 36-45 YEARS	BETWEEN 46-55 YEARS	ABOVE 55 YEARS	TOTAL
STRONGLY AGREE	14	4	11	0	0	29
AGREE	52	4	3	3	0	62
NEITHER AGREE NOR DISAGREE	16	9	0	18	6	49
DISAGREE	3	1	1	2	0	7
STRONGLY DISAGREE	2	0	0	1	0	3
TOTAL	87	18	15	24	6	150

EXPECTED VALUES (E)

$[(87*29)/150]$ 16.82	=	$[(18*29)/150]$ 3.48	=	$[(15*29)/150]$ 2.9	=	$[(24*29)/150]$ 4.64	=	$[(6*29)/150]$ 1.16
$[(87*62)/150]$ 35.96	=	$[(18*62)/150]$ 7.44	=	$[(15*62)/150]$ 6.2	=	$[(24*62)/150]$ 9.92	=	$[(6*62)/150]$ 2.48
$[(87*49)/150]$ 28.42	=	$[(18*49)/150]$ 5.88	=	$[(15*49)/150]$ 4.9	=	$[(24*49)/150]$ 7.84	=	$[(6*49)/150]$ 1.96
$[(87*7)/150] = 4.06$	=	$[(18*7)/150]$ 0.84	=	$[(15*7)/150] = 0.7$	=	$[(24*7)/150]$ 1.12	=	$[(6*7)/150]$ 0.28
$[(87*3)/150] = 1.74$	=	$[(18*3)/150]$ 0.36	=	$[(15*3)/150] = 0.3$	=	$[(24*3)/150]$ 0.48	=	$[(6*3)/150]$ 0.12

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	$\chi^2 = \sum (O-E)^2 / E$
14	16.82	-2.82	7.95	0.47
4	3.48	0.52	0.27	0.08
11	2.9	8.1	65.61	22.62
0	4.64	-4.64	21.53	4.64
0	1.16	-1.16	1.35	1.16
52	35.96	16.04	257.28	7.15
4	7.44	-3.44	11.83	1.59
3	6.2	-3.2	10.24	1.65
3	9.92	-6.92	47.89	4.83
0	2.48	-2.48	6.15	2.48
16	28.42	-12.42	154.26	5.43
9	5.88	3.12	9.73	1.65
0	4.9	-4.9	24.01	4.9
18	7.84	10.16	103.23	13.17
6	1.96	4.04	16.32	8.33
3	4.06	-1.06	1.12	0.28
1	0.84	0.16	0.03	0.04
1	0.7	0.3	0.09	0.13
2	1.12	0.88	0.77	0.69
0	0.28	-0.28	0.08	0.29
2	1.74	0.26	0.07	0.04
0	0.36	-0.36	0.13	0.36
0	0.3	-0.3	0.09	0.3
1	0.48	0.52	0.27	0.56
0	0.12	-0.12	0.01	0.08
				82.92

Calculated Value = 82.92

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Degree Of Freedom} &= (r-1) * (c-1) \\
 &= (5-1) * (5-1) \\
 &= 4*4 \\
 &= 16
 \end{aligned}$$

Where,

r = number of rows.

c = number of columns.

Tabulated Chi-Square value at 5% Significant Level = 26.296

Results: The calculated value (82.92) > tabulated value (26.296) hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate Hypothesis is acknowledged.

Inference:

The calculated value is greater than the Tabulated Value, therefore alternate Hypothesis is accepted. There exists a significant relationship between age and the safety measures provided by the company.

- I. Connection between gender and motivation by superiors in the work place

Ho: There seems to be no corelation between gender and motivation by superiors in the work place.

H1: There is corelation between gender and motivation by superiors in the work place.

Observed values (O)

	HIGHLY SATISFIED	SATISFIED	NEITHER SATISFIED NOR DISSATISFIED	DISSATISFIED	HIGHLY DISSATISFIED	TOTAL
FEMALE	32	45	62	7	4	150

Expected Frequency (E)

$[(32*94)/150] = 20.05$	$[(45*94)/150] = 28.2$	$[(62*94)/150] = 38.85$	$[(7*94)/150] = 4.39$	$[(4*94)/150] = 2.51$
$[(32*56)/150] = 11.95$	$[(45*56)/150] = 16.8$	$[(62*56)/150] = 23.14$	$[(7*56)/150] = 2.61$	$[(4*56)/150] = 1.49$

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum(O-E)^2}{E}$
20	20.05	-0.05	0	0
35	28.2	6.8	46.24	1.64
34	38.85	-4.85	23.52	0.61
3	4.39	-1.39	1.93	0.44
2	2.51	-0.51	0.26	0.10
12	11.95	0.05	0	0
10	16.8	-6.8	46.24	2.75
28	23.14	4.86	23.62	1.02
4	2.61	1.39	1.93	0.74
2	1.49	0.51	0.26	0.17
				7.47

Calculated Value = 7.47

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Degree Of Freedom} &= (r-1) * (c-1) \\
 &= (2-1) * (5-1) \\
 &= 1 * 4 \\
 &= 4
 \end{aligned}$$

Where,

r = number of rows.

c = number of columns.

**Tabulated Chi-Square value at 5%
Significant Level = 9.488**

Results: The calculated value (7.47) < tabulated value (9.488) hence, null hypothesis is accepted and alternate Hypothesis is rejected.

INFERENCE:

Because the calculated value is lower than the Tabulated Value, the null hypothesis is supported. There is no substantial link between gender and superior motivation in the workplace.

FINDINGS:

- Majority of the respondents are below 25 years of age.
- Majority of the respondents have degree as Educational Qualification.
- Most of the respondents agree that they are provided with basic facilities for performing the work.
- Most of the respondents are satisfied with the motivation given by the superiors in the work place.
- Majority of the respondents are contented with the working time.
- Majority of the respondents agree that the safety measures provided are satisfactory.

SUGGESTIONS

- Conflict management system should be made active, in order to solve the disputes arising within the organisation.
- Training should be given, as such; it helps in improving the relationship with employees.
- The motivation provided by the superior must be improved.
- The fringe benefits provided by the company must be increased.
- The safety measures taken in the workplace must be increased.
- The suggestion schemes followed must be improved as a way to increase the participation and commitment of the employees.
- The employees must be given freedom to make changes in their job, which may helps to perform the job well.

CONCLUSION

The research focuses primarily on job factors, interpersonal relationships, and intrinsic motivators, work schedules, and atmosphere as dimensions related to the Quality of Work Life. These parameters were discovered to be equally crucial in assessing and outlining the work-life quality policies.

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